

Complexities in Managing 12 Cases of Primary Amenorrhea in a Rural Tertiary Centre in North Bihar: A Retrospective Case Series**Zaheena¹, Pooja Sinha², Swapan Kumar Kundu³, Soumyajyoti Kundu⁴**^{1,2}Junior Resident, Dept. of OBGYN, MGM Medical College, Kishanganj, Bihar³Professor, Dept. of OBGYN, MGM Medical College, Kishanganj, Bihar⁴Junior Resident, Dept. of Microbiology, ICARE Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Haldia, West Bengal

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This case-series was compiled in a span of 11 months to identify most common cause of Primary Amenorrhea among cases attending GOPD and to depict the various modalities of treatment in such cases in MGM Medical College, Kishanganj, a Rural Tertiary Care Hospital in North-East Bihar. The mean age was found to be 14.8 years, most of them (58.3%) were in Upper Lower Class. The incidence of Primary Amenorrhea was 5.5% among adolescent patients attending gynae OPD and the most common cause of Primary Amenorrhea was Mullerian Agenesis (16.6%). Management was done by Multidisciplinary approach based on aetio-pathology.

Keywords: Primary, Amenorrhoea, Mullerian, Agenesis,

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Introduction

Primary amenorrhea is absence of menses by 13 years of age in the absence of growth or development of secondary sexual characteristics or, absence of menses by 15 years of age regardless of the presence of normal growth and development including secondary sexual characteristics. [1]

It affects 2%–5% of all women in reproductive age.

Timely evaluation and consideration of a broad differential diagnosis have important implications for quality of life, emotional, physical and reproductive health in young women.

Objectives:

Primary: To identify most common cause of Primary Amenorrhea among cases attending GOPD, in MGM Medical College, Kishanganj, a Rural Tertiary Care Hospital in North-East Bihar. [2]

Secondary:

- To know the incidence of Primary Amenorrhea among patients attending GOPD.
- To depict the various modalities of treatment in cases with Primary Amenorrhea.

Methodology:

Period of study: months (January - November 2023).

Place of study: Gynaec. OPD, MGM Medical College.

Study population: All cases of primary amenorrhea attending OPD.

Work up: History, clinical examination, investigations (UPT negative & other laboratory findings and imaging).

Informed and written consent from Parents/Legal Guardians were taken.

Management: Multidisciplinary approach based on aetio-pathology.

Results:

- Age:** Mean age 14.8 years.
- SE Status (B.G Prasad classification):** 16.6% Lower Class, 58.3% Upper Lower Class, 25% Lower Middle Class.
- Literacy:** 33.3% school going, 41.6% primary education and 25% illiterate.
- Population:** Rural.
- Co-morbidities:** 8.3% overweight (BMI – 23.83), 8.3% obese (BMI-25.81) and 41.6% underweight (BMI 17.78), 2 had hypothyroidism, 1 had tuberculosis, 1 had skeletal defects, 1 had psychiatric disorder, 1 had surgical history, 1 had history of chemotherapy.
- Incidence of Primary Amenorrhea:** 5.5% among adolescent patients attending gynae OPD.

7. The most common cause of Primary Amenorrhea: Mullerian Agenesis (16.6%).

8. Management: Multidisciplinary approach based on aetio-pathology.

CASE	Afsaana Khatoon Sirat	Lakshmi Kumari	Fatma Parveen	Nusrat Jahan	Rokiya Khatoon	Roji Khatoon	Arshi	Jannatun Nisha	kailashi kumari	Nasreen Khatoo	Rizwana Khatoo		
History	Age(years)	15	15	14	14	16	15	16	15	15	14	15	
Chief complaint	absent menses	absent menses	absent menses	absent menses	absent menses	absent menses	discharge from E	referred from pe	absent menses	absent menses	absent menses	absent menses	
Family history	NA	NA	diagnosed pulm	NA	elder sister with	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
associated medical his	NA	NA	fever, weight los	NA	NA	hair loss and we	NA	under evaluation k/o scoliosis	Diagnosed and t	Diagnosed case	h/o surgery for p		
Examination	Height(cm)	153	160	151	152	150	155	148	133	138	150	152	136
	Weight(kg)	52	61	40	43	38	62	50	32	40	41	42	38
	BMI	22.21	23.83	17.54	18.61	16.89	25.81	22.83	18.09	21	18.22	18.18	20.54
	Breast Tanner stage	3	2	1	2	3	3	4	4	2	2	2	1
	Pubic hair Tanner stage	3	2	1	2	3	3	2	1	1	2	1	1
	Axillary hair	present	present	absent	present	present	present	present	absent	present	present	present	absent
	Associated findings	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	facial puffiness, Shield chest, we	NA	NA	NA	NA
	External Genitalia	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
	Palpation	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
	P/S examination	Blunt vagina	Blunt vagina	WNL	Bluish bludge +	WNL	WNL	WNL	WNL	WNL	-	WNL	WNL
	P/V examination	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PIR examination	uterine border co	consent not give	uterus fixed with	uterine bulge +	WNL	WNL	WNL	Small size of ute	WNL	-	-	-
Investigations	UPT	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative
	S. FSH (m IU/ml)	4.7	3.97	5.2	4.2	5.64	3.82	5.26	7.9	73.74	22.4	4.8	41.6
	S. LH (m IU/ml)	3.2	4.53	2.6	5.2	3.94	4.91	2.1	0.4	23.02	18	4.6	20.8
	S. Prolactin (mg/ml)	12.3	13.4	16	14.2	17.4	14.8	172.2	71.1	15.28	18.46	62.4	12.46
	S. Testosterone (ng/ml)	41	38.2	32.4	31.2	45.6	28.65	23.48	-	9.24	-	35.8	8.42
	S. Estradiol (pg/ml)	53.6	180	72.8	84.4	66.72	78.4	28.6	-	18	19.6	40.56	16.42
	S. TSH (uIU/mL)	0.79	1.24	1.62	0.86	1.58	78.949	1.88	150	1.93	2.24	1.28	2.68
	USG	Cord like structur	Crossed fused ri	B/L tubes dilated	Hematocolpos w	Normal study	Pelvis-Normal st	Normal study	Pelvis-bulky righ	Rudimentary ute	Normal study	Normal study	Infantile uterus w
	CT/MRI	-	-	Mild enhancing c	f/s/o hematocolp	-	-	F/S/O Pituitary	Pituitary gland is	Uterine hypoplas	-	-	-
	Karyotyping	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	45-XO	-	-	-	-
	Additional investigator	-	-	Hysterolaproscop	-	-	T.T-4.3.8ug/dL T:-	-	x-ray wrist- Diffu	AMH-<0.13ng/m	AMH-0.8ng/mL	-	AMH 0.28ng/mL
Management	Diagnosis	MRKH-A	MRKH-B	Genital tubercul	Imperforated hyr	Suspected Cons	Hypothyroidism	Prolactinoma	Pickardt syndron	Turner's Syndron	Chemotherapy ir	Drug induced by	Primary amanorr
	Management	-	-	ATT	Crutiate hymen i	Counselling don	medical manage	cabergoline	cabergoline and	HRT	HRT	cabergoline alon	HRT
	Counselling	Extensive	Extensive	Extensive	for followup	Extensive	done	for follow up	extensive	extensive	extensive	for follow up	extensive

Discussion

Case 1 [MRKH-A]:

A 15 years old unmarried girl with negative urine pregnancy test, presented with complaint of absent menses. There was no associated family or medical or surgical history. On examination patient had a height of 153cm, weight of 52kgs and BMI of 22.21, breasts had Tanner staging of 3 and pubic hair Tanner staging of 3. External genitalia appeared normal. [3] Per speculum examination showed blunt vagina and uterine border could not be made out in

per rectal examination. Blood examination showed S. FSH 4.7 mIU/ml, S. LH 3.2 m IU/ml, S. Prolactin 12.3 mg/ml, S. Testosterone 41 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 53.6 pg/ml, S. TSH 0.79 uIU/mL, USG suggested Cord like structure noted in the region of uterus-likely severely dysplastic uterus, additional investigations were not done due to monitory insufficiency. [4] she was diagnosed as a case of MRKH-A and extensive counselling alongside parents was done. [5]

Case 2 [MRKH-B]:

A 15 years old unmarried girl with negative urine pregnancy test, presented with complaint of absent menses. There was no associated family or medical or surgical history. On examination patient had a height of 160cm, weight of 61kgs and BMI of 23.83, breast showed Tanner staging of 2 and pubic hair Tanner staging of 2. External genitalia appeared normal. Per speculum examination showed blunt vagina and per rectal examination was denied by

patient. Blood examination showed S. FSH 3.97mIU/ml, S. LH 4.53 m IU/ml, S. Prolactin 13.4 mg/ml, S. Testosterone 38.2 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 160pg/ml, S. TSH 1.24 uIU/mL, USG suggested Crossed fused right kidney, hypochoic band like structure noted in region of uterus and cervix, additional investigations were not done due to monitory insufficiency. she was diagnosed as a case of MRKH-B and extensive counselling alongside parents was done. [6]

CASE 3 [Disseminated Tuberculosis]: A 14 years old unmarried girl with negative urine pregnancy test, presented with complaint of absent menses. She was recently diagnosed and being treated for

extrapulmonary tuberculosis. She belonged to underprivileged and low socio-economic status and family history of pulmonary tuberculosis in father who was a defaulter of treatment. On examination

patient had a height of 151cm, weight of 40kgs and BMI of 17.54, breast Tanner staging of 1 and pubic hair Tanner staging of 1. External genitalia appeared normal. [7] Per speculum examination showed normal vagina and per rectal examination suggested uterus fixed with absent mobility. Blood examination showed S. FSH 5.2mIU/ml, S. LH 2.6 m IU/ml, S. Prolactin 16mg/ml, S. Testosterone 32.4 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 72.8pg/ml, S. TSH 1.62 uIU/mL, USG showed B/L tubes dilated, thickened with evidence of pus; i.e. suspected pyosalpinx, CEMRI showed Mild enhancing circumferential thickening of terminal ileum, ileocecal junction, with abdominal and mediastinal lymphadenopathy

as described- s/o infective etiology, likely tubercular B/L pleural thickening is noted (Lt> Rt), Multiple lymph nodes in anterior and posterior mediastinum and B/L hilar region, fibrotic bands are noted in B/L upper lung fields. [8] Hystero-laproscopy showed presence of uterine synechia, ostia not visualized, B/L tube congested and oedematous, with Histology: epithelioid granuloma with caseous necrosis, and culture: M. tuberculosis. she was diagnosed as a case of Genital tuberculosis and continued Anti-tubercular treatment.

[9]

CASE 4 [Imperforate Hymen]: A 14 years old unmarried girl with negative urine pregnancy test, presented with complaint of absent menses with cyclical pain abdomen for 6 months. There was no associated family or medical or surgical history. On examination patient had a height of 152cm, weight of 43kgs and BMI of 18.61, breast Tanner staging of 2 and pubic hair Tanner staging of 2. External genitalia appeared normal. Per speculum examination showed Bluish bulge with intact hymen and per rectal examination suggested mobile uterine

bulge. Blood examination showed S. FSH 4.2mIU/ml, S. LH 5.2 m IU/ml, S. Prolactin 14.2mg/ml, S. Testosterone 31.2 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 84.4pg/ml, S. TSH 0.86 uIU/mL, USG showed Hematocolpos with hematometra, CEMRI showed f/s/o Hematocolpos secondary to vaginal severely hypoplasia and lower segment atresia. she was diagnosed as a case of Imperforated hymen (Cryptomenorrhea) and treated via Cruciate hymen incision with drainage of collected blood.

CASE 5 [Constitutional Delay]: A 16 years old unmarried girl with negative urine pregnancy test, presented with complaint of absent menses. Elder sister had a history of delayed onset of menarche. On examination patient had a height of 150cm, weight of 38kgs and BMI of 16.89, breast Tanner staging of 3 and pubic hair Tanner staging of 3. External genitalia appeared normal. Per speculum examination showed normal vagina and per rectal

examination suggested normal uterus. Blood examination showed S. FSH 5.64mIU/ml, S. LH 3.94 m IU/ml, S. Testosterone 45.6 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 66.72 pg/ml, S. Prolactin 17.4mg/ml, S. Testosterone 45.6 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 66.72pg/ml, S. TSH 1.58 uIU/mL, USG showed normal finding. she was diagnosed as a case of Constitutional Delay and adequate counselling along with follow up was done.

CASE 6 [Hypothyroidism]:

A 15 years old unmarried girl with negative urine pregnancy test, presented with a complaint of absent menses. She has % hair loss and weight gain in past 1 year. On examination patient had a height of 155cm weight of 62kgs and BMI of 25.81, breast Tanner staging of 3 and pubic hair Tanner staging of 3. External genitalia appeared normal. Per speculum examination showed normal vagina and per rectal

examination suggested uterus fixed with absent mobility. Blood examination showed S. FSH 3.82 mIU/ml, S. LH 4.91 m IU/ml, S. Testosterone 28.65 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 76.4 pg/ml, S. Prolactin 14.8 mg/ml, S. Testosterone 28.65 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 76.4 pg/ml, S. TSH 78.949 uIU/mL, S.T4-3.8ug/dL T3-0.51ng/mL Anti-TPO-<28.0IU/mL. USG pelvis and neck showed normal findings. she was diagnosed as a case of Hypothyroidism and started on 100mcg of levothyroxine.

TEST PARAMETERS	RESULT	NORMAL RANGE
HORMONE ASSAY		
T ₄	0.51 ng/dl	0.5-1.9 ng/dl
T ₃	3.8 ug/dl	4.4-11.6 ug/dl
TSH	78.99 uIU/ml	0.3-4.0 uIU/ml
LH	4.91 mIU/ml	
FSH	3.82 mIU/ml	
PROLACTIN	14.8 ng/ml	1.2-19.5 ng/ml
FT ₄	ng/dl	1.4-4.2 ng/dl
FT ₃	ng/dl	0.8-2.2 ng/dl
hCG	mIU/ml	0.1-5.7 mIU/ml
IgE	IU/ml	0-200 IU/ml
Anti TPO	< 28.0 IU/mL	0-34 IU/mL

CASE 7 [Prolactinoma]:

A 16 years old unmarried girl with negative urine pregnancy test, presented with complaints of absent menses and discharge from B/L nipple and Pain for 15 days. There was no associated family or medical or surgical history. On examination patient had a height of 148cm, weight of 50kgs and BMI of 22.83, breast Tanner staging of 4 and pubic hair Tanner staging of 2. External genitalia appeared normal. Per speculum and per rectal examination showed normal

vagina and uterus respectively. Blood examination showed S. FSH 5.26 mIU/ml, S. LH 2.1m IU/ml, S. Testosterone 23.48 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 28.6 pg/ml, S. Prolactin 172.2 mg/ml, S. Testosterone 23.48 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 28.6 pg/ml, S. TSH 1.88 uIU/mL, USG pelvis suggested normal finding, NCCT showed F/S/O Pituitary Macroadenoma. she was diagnosed as a case of Prolactinoma and treated by cabergoline 0.5mg twice weekly for 6weeks and follow up.

TEST PARAMETERS	RESULT	NORMAL RANGE
T ₁	0.02 ng/ml	0.5-1.9 ng/ml
T ₂	8.26 µg/dl	4.4-11.6 µg/dl
TSH	1.88 µIU/ml	0.3-6.0 µIU/ml
LH	5.2 mIU/ml	
FSH	5.2 mIU/ml	
PROLACTIN	172.2 ng/ml	1.2-19.5 ng/ml
FT ₁		1.4-4.2 ng/dl
FT ₂		0.8-2.2 ng/dl
DRUG		0.1-5.7 mIU/ml
lgE		0-200 IU/ml
E ₂	8.6	40-70

CASE 8 [Congenital Hypothyroidism + Hyperprolactinemia - Pickardt's Syndrome]:

A 16 years old unmarried girl with negative urine pregnancy test, under evaluation for short stature with primary hypothyroidism presented with complaint of absent menses. There was no associated family history. On examination patient had a height of 133cm weight of 32kgs and BMI of 18.09, breast Tanner staging of 4 and pubic hair Tanner staging of 1, facial puffiness, shield chest, inverted nipple with oedematous areola. External genitalia appeared normal. Per speculum and per rectal examination showed normal vagina and uterus respectively. Blood examination showed S. FSH 7.9

mIU/ml, S. LH 0.4 m IU/ml, S.Prolactin 71.1 mg/ml, S. TSH 150 uIU/mL, USG Pelvis-bulky right ovary; neck-f/s/o thyroiditis likely of autoimmune etiology in a background of hypothyroidism, No evidence of heterogeneously enhancing lesion in pituitary gland-likely secondary to chronic hypothyroidism or organ failure. MRI-brain showed Pituitary gland is diffuse enlarged, indicating hyperplasia with maintained dorsal concave margin. x-ray wrist- Diffuse osteogenic changes and AMA- >1000IU/mL; Anti-TG- 21.8IU/mL. she was diagnosed as a case of *Pickardt's Syndrome* and treated on cabergoline 0.5mg weekly for 4 weeks and levothyroxine 100mcg OD and follow up.

Gender/Age	: Female / 15 Years	Patient ID No.	: 150217 / 22-24 (PP)
Consultant Dr.	: Dr. DESHPANDE UNTI	Registered On	: 22/02/2023 09:25 AM
		Collected On	: 22/02/2023 12:42 PM
		Reported On	: 22/02/2023 11:11 PM

TEST DESCRIPTION	ORDERED VALUE	REFERENCE RANGES/UNITS
SODIUM	137	135-140 meq/L
POTASSIUM	3.5	3.5-5.0 meq/L
CALCIUM	9.0	8.8-10.0 mg/dl
CHLORIDE	98	98-109 mmol/L
TSH	1.93	0.4-2.0 uIU/ml
PROLACTIN	15.28	1.2-19.8 ng/ml
FSH	73.74	mIU/ml

End of Report

Referred by: - PANDYA BINOD D
OPD/PPD No: - 1-369
Part Examined: - MRI BRAIN
Date: - 11/09/2023

MRI - BRAIN WITHOUT IV CONTRAST

Imaging Technique: MR examination of the brain was performed using a dedicated head coil. ALPS, 10 T1, 8 T2, 12 weighted images obtained in the axial plane, T1 T2 sagittal and coronal. (List and etc)

OBSERVATIONS:

- Pituitary gland is diffuse enlarged, indicating hyperplasia with maintained dorsal convex margin. No evidence of heterogeneously enhancing lesion in pituitary gland.
- The pituitary stalk is thinned but is still present with intact arterial supply resulting in diffuse homogeneous enhancement of gland.

GENERAL HEMISPHERE: Normal.
INTRACRANIAL HEMISPHERE: Normal.
MIDLINE EFFECT / MIDLINE SHIFT: Normal.
THALAMIC & BASAL GANGLIA: Normal.
VENTRICLES, CORTICAL SULCI, SPINIFOLIA FISSURES & BASAL CYSTERNI: Normal.
MIDBRAN, PONS, MEDULLA: Normal.
CEREBELLUM: Normal.
SELLA: Normal.
ORBITS: Normal.
VITRALIZED INTRACRANIAL ARTERIAL FLOW VELOCITY: Normal.
DURAL VENOUS SINUSES FLOW VELOCITY: Normal.
VITRALIZED PARANASAL SINUSES: Normal.
CALVARIAL: Normal.
SUPERFICIAL SOFT TISSUE SCALP: Normal.

IMPRESSION:

- Pituitary gland is diffuse enlarged, indicating hyperplasia with maintained dorsal convex margin. No evidence of heterogeneously enhancing lesion in pituitary gland - Likely secondary to chronic hypopituitarism or organ failure.

Act: - Serum, prolactin level is rule out the possibility of partial stalk interruption (pituitary apoplexy).

Note: This is only a Radiological Impression & not a Diagnosis and has its limitations. Therefore it should be interpreted in correlation with clinical &/or pathologic findings.

CASE 9 [Turner’s Syndrome]:

A 15 years old unmarried girl with negative urine pregnancy test, k/c/o Turner’s syndrome presented with complaint of absent menses. There was no associated family history. On examination patient had a height of 138cm, weight of 40kgs and BMI of 21, breast Tanner staging of 1 and pubic hair Tanner staging of 1, Shield chest, webbed neck, low hairline, scoliosis. External genitalia appeared normal. Per speculum and per rectal examination

showed normal vagina and small sized uterus respectively. Blood examination showed S. FSH 73.74 mIU/ml, S. LH 23.02 m IU/ml, S. Testosterone 9.24 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 18 pg/ml, S. Prolactin 15.28 mg/ml, S. TSH 1.93 uIU/mL, AMH <0.13ng/mL, USG Pelvis-Rudimentary uterus, right and left ovaries cannot be assessed. MRI-Pelvis Uterine hypoplasia with streak ovaries. Karyotyping showed 45-XO Genotype. She was diagnosed as a case of *Primary Amenorrhea d/t turner’s syndrome* and started on HRT, counselling and follow up.

Referred by: - OBS & GYNAE
OPD/PPD No: 213006
Part Examined: PELVIS
Date: 25/09/2023

MRI - PELVIS (PLAIN T2 WITHOUT IV CONTRAST):

Imaging Technique: Coronal - 5/16, T2WI Axial - 12/15, T2WI Sag - 12/15.

OBSERVATIONS:

- URINARY BLADDER: Normal.
- UTERUS: A small for age, hypoplastic uterus of size 5 x 1.7 x 2.5 cm (AP x TR x CC) is noted. A thinned out endometrium (~ 1.5 mm) is noted with maintained normal configuration.
- VAGINA & CERVIX: Normal.
- OVARIES: Both ovaries are small and atrophic, without any definite follicles.
- FLUID: Mild free fluid is seen in POD.
- LYMPH NODES: NA.
- RECTUM, ANAL CANAL & VESICULATED BOWEL: Normal.
- VISUALIZED SPINE: Normal.

IMPRESSION:

- Features favor hypoplastic uterus with atrophic ovaries as described above (USINCOVOESHRE classification).

Note: This is only a Radiological Impression & not a Diagnosis and has its limitations. Therefore it should be interpreted in correlation with clinical &/or pathologic findings.

Referred by: - PANDYA BINOD D
OPD/PPD No: - 1-369
Part Examined: - MRI BRAIN
Date: - 11/09/2023

TEST PARAMETERS	RESULT	NORMAL RANGE
TSH	1.93	0.4-2.0 uIU/ml
FSH	73.74	mIU/ml
LH	23.02	mIU/ml
PROLACTIN	15.28	ng/ml
TESTOSTERONE	9.24	ng/ml
ESTRADIOL	18	pg/ml
AMH	<0.13	ng/ml

Referred by: - OBS & GYNAE
OPD/PPD No: - 2271012
Part Examined: - PELVIC
DATE: - 11/12/2023

ULTRASOUND OF PELVIC

Urinary bladder: Normal in distension, outline and wall thickness. No internal echoes seen.

Uterus & Cervix: is hypoplastic & small in size (6 x 2.3 x 3.3) cm. Endometrial stripe is thinned out (4 mm).

Ovaries & Adnexae:

- Right ovary: is small in size (vol - 1 cc) with no evidence of any dominant follicles.
- Left ovary: is small in size (vol - 1 cc) with no evidence of any dominant follicles.

No free fluid seen.

Impression: USG Findings are suggestive of -
 > **Hypoplastic uterus and ovaries.**

Act: - MRI pelvis.

CASE 10 [Chemotherapy induced]:

A 15 years old unmarried girl with negative urine pregnancy test, Diagnosed and treated case of ALL 3years back; induction regimen (4week)- cyclophosphamide, vincristine, daunorubicin, L-asparaginase and prednisone maintenance regimen(2year)- 6-MP, methotrexate, vincristine and prednisone. There was no associated family history. On examination patient had a height of 150cm, weight of 41kgs and BMI of 18.22, breast

Tanner staging of 2 and pubic hair Tanner staging of 2. External genitalia appeared normal. Per speculum and per rectal examination showed normal vagina and uterus respectively. Blood examination showed S. FSH 22.4 mIU/ml, S. LH 18 m IU/ml, S. Estradiol 19.6 pg/ml, S. Prolactin 18.46 mg/ml, S. TSH 2.24 uIU/mL, AMH-0.89ng/mL, USG Pelvis-normal. She was diagnosed as a case of Chemotherapy induced POI and started on HRT, counselling and follow up.

Referred by	Unit	
Regd. No.	Bed No.	Date
Sample :		
TEST PARAMETERS	RESULT	NORMAL RANGE
HORMONE ASSAY		
T ₃	_____ ng/ml	0.5-1.9 ng/ml
T ₄	_____ µg/dl	4.4-11.6 µg/dl
TSH	2.24 µIU/ml	0.3-6.0 µIU/ml
LH	18.0 mIU/ml	
FSH	22.4 mIU/ml	
PROLACTIN	18.46 ng/ml	1.2-19.5 ng/ml
FT ₃	_____ ng/dl	1.4-4.2 ng/dl
FT ₄	_____ ng/dl	0.8-2.2 ng/dl
βhCG	_____ mIU/ml	0.1-5.7 mIU/ml
IgE	_____ IU/ml	0-200 IU/ml
S-AMH	<0.80 ng/mL	1.5-4 ng/mL

CASE 11 [Drug induced hyperprolactinemia]:

A 14 years old unmarried girl with negative urine pregnancy test, Diagnosed case of Autistic spectrum disorder for 3 years with self-injury, aggression, irritability and destructive tendencies- on Risperidone for 1 year -2mg/day. There was no associated family history. On examination patient had a height of 152cm weight of 42kgs and BMI of 18.18, breast Tanner staging of 2 and pubic hair Tanner staging of 1. External genitalia appeared

normal. Per speculum and per rectal examination showed normal vagina and uterus respectively. Blood examination showed S. FSH 4.8 mIU/ml, S. LH 4.6 m IU/ml, S. Testosterone 30.8 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 40.56 pg/ml, S. Prolactin 62.4 mg/ml, S. TSH 1.28 uIU/mL, USG Pelvis-normal. She was diagnosed as a case of Drug-induced hyperprolactinemia and started on cabergoline along with reduction of Risperidone dose/ use of alternative drug, counselling and follow up.

Referred by	Unit	
Regd. No.	Bed No.	Date
Sample :		
TEST PARAMETERS	RESULT	NORMAL RANGE
HORMONE ASSAY		
T ₃	_____ ng/ml	0.5-1.9 ng/ml
T ₄	_____ µg/dl	4.4-11.6 µg/dl
TSH	1.28 µIU/ml	0.3-6.0 µIU/ml
LH	4.6 mIU/ml	
FSH	4.8 mIU/ml	
PROLACTIN	62.4 ng/ml	1.2-19.5 ng/ml
FT ₃	_____ ng/dl	1.4-4.2 ng/dl
FT ₄	_____ ng/dl	0.8-2.2 ng/dl
βhCG	_____ mIU/ml	0.1-5.7 mIU/ml
IgE	_____ IU/ml	0-200 IU/ml

CASE 12 [Surgically Induced/Iatrogenic]:

A 15 years old unmarried girl with negative urine pregnancy test, h/o surgery for pelvic tumor (no documentation) 3 years back. There was no associated family history. On examination, patient had a height of 136cm, weight of 38kgs and BMI of 20.54, breast Tanner staging of 1 and pubic hair Tanner staging of 1. External genitalia appeared normal. Per speculum and per rectal examination

showed normal vagina and uterus respectively. Blood examination showed S. FSH 41.6 mIU/ml, S. LH 20.8 m IU/ml, S. Testosterone 8.42 ng/ml, S. Estradiol 16.42 pg/ml, S. Prolactin 12.46 mg/ml, S. TSH 2.68 uIU/mL, AMH 0.28ng/mL, USG Pelvis-Infantile uterus with B/L ovaries cannot be visualised (H/O surgical removal). She was diagnosed as a case of Primary amenorrhea secondary to B/L oophorectomy and started on HRT, counselling and follow up.

SUMMARY:		
MRKH - (A&B)	2	(16.6%)
Disseminated Tuberculosis	1	(8.3%)
Cryptomenorrhea	1	(8.3%)
Constitutional delay	1	(8.3%)
Hypothyroidism	1	(8.3%)
Prolactinoma	1	(8.3%)
Pickardt's Syndrome	1	(8.3%)
Turner's Syndrome	1	(8.3%)
Chemotherapy Induced	1	(8.3%)
Drug Induced Hyperprolactinemia	1	(8.3%)
Surgically induced	1	(8.3%)

Comparative Studies:

1.	Sumita Verma et al. Case Series of Primary Amenorrhoea at PMCH, Patna. IJSDR, v8, Jan 23: 1056-1060	1.5%	Gonadal Dysgenesis (44%)
2.	Pavanaganga A et al. Int J Reprod Contracept ObstetGynecol. 2019 Sep;8(9):3442-3444	2.0	MRKH (36%)
3.	Kriplani A et al. Aetiology and management of primary amenorrhoea: a study of 102 cases at tertiary centre. Taiwan J Obstet Gynaecol. 2017;56(6):761-4.	3.0%	Mullerian agenesis (47%)
4.	Anitha GS et al. Clinical study of primary amenorrhoea. J South Asian Federation Obstet Gynaecol. 2015;7(3):158	2.5	Complete AIS (60%)
5.	Tanmahasamut P. et al (2012), Causes of primary amenorrhoea: A report of 295 cases in Thailand. Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Research, 38: 297-30	2.2%	Müllerian agenesis (39.7%)
6.	Our Study 2023	5.5%	MRKH (16.6%)

Conclusion:

1. Most common cause of Primary Amenorrhoea- Mullerian Agenesis (16.6%).

2. Incidence of Primary Amenorrhoea- 5.5% [12/217] among adolescent patient attending gynae OPD, MGM Medical College.

3. Management- Multidisciplinary approach including social bodies like NGO's.

Limitations of our Study:

1. It is a small-scale study for short duration.
2. Loss of follow-up due to social stigma.
3. Monitory restrictions for advanced investigations.

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Informed Consent: Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for their anonymized information to be published in this article.

Patient Consent: Informed written consent has been obtained from the patient for all case details and images to be reported in the journal.

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